

METHODS OF PERFORMING COMPUTER CONTROLLED EMI COMPLIANCE TESTS

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Abstract : Increasingly, companies and laboratories are switching over from the standard, manually controlled, EMI compliance test equipment to new automated systems. These new systems are useful because they can drastically reduce the time and effort to perform EMI tests. However, these systems require forethought and careful planning in their use. This paper details some of the problems we have encountered in the use of automated systems, and recommendations for resolving these problems.

Example 1. One particular system put an unexpected 4.5 kHz signal on radiated magnetic flux (MIL-STD-461 RE01) data while it was unattended [1]. Upon performing a real time analysis it was found that an unrelated environmental test, in an adjacent laboratory, was intermittently emitting a powerful 4.5 kHz signal.

Since it can take an hour for the computer controlled system to perform a test such as RE01, it is unreasonable to expect someone to monitor every minute of the test. A selling point for ATE is its supervision-free aspect, but it can be a source of error .

Unexpected Shortcomings of Automated Testing

New Types of Operator Error

Operators who are proficient in performing EMC compliance testing with standard, manually operated, test systems are often unfamiliar with the operation of automated (i.e. computer controlled) test equipment (ATE). There is a willingness to let the computer run "open loop" (i.e.. since ATE manufacturer said it can do everything perfect, one can go have coffee !).

When test engineers and technicians are presented with the latest in ATE, there is also a tendency to operate it without first considering all the implications of such a setup. The resulting errors in the data are often not found until the completion of the testing, if ever.

Human intervention during the performance of EMI testing, especially automated EMI testing, should not be overlooked.

Two examples showing the importance of real time analysis and transient effects on unattended systems are given:

Example 2. A system employing a swept oscillator was being evaluated for compliance to MIL-STD-461 and failed. Upon retest, the frequency of the failure changed. The peak hold feature was not software selectable for this particular ATE. In order to properly evaluate the failure, it was necessary to manually employ the peak hold feature of the EMI test instrumentation , while allowing both the equipment under test (EUT) and test instrumentation to respond to several cycles of the swept oscillator. This showed that the failure really occurred over the entire frequency range of the swept oscillator.

Data is Manipulated by the Computer

Automated measurement systems perform a variety of operations prior to presenting the "final" data. The automated measurement systems, along with controlling the test equipment, account for amplifier / attenuator settings, probe calibration factors, bandwidth correction factors, etc. when preparing the final data for presentation [2]. In doing so, the automated measurement systems perform the tedious work previously performed by the engineer or technician performing the test, and saves valuable time and money.

A pitfall in allowing the automated measurement system to operate in this manner is the way which the majority of systems perform their corrections. These automated measurement systems all tend to add the required "correction factors" (i.e. amplifier / attenuator settings, probe calibration factors, bandwidth correction factors, etc.) directly to the analyzer output. This permanently modifies the data and, if an incorrect correction factor is chosen by the operator, possibly ruins the data .

Availability of Original Data : When automated measurement systems add all of the correction factors directly to the original analyzer data, it obscures this data. This original data is essentially an "unknown" quantity. The correction factors are verifiable quantities. Adding the analyzer data to the correction factors results in a "modified unknown" quantity, the reduced data.

$$\text{original data} + \text{correction factors} = \text{reduced data} \quad (1)$$

Automated measurement systems using this method do not allow reviewers to examine the analyzer data in order to verify that the data reduction was performed properly. The correction factors must be removed from the reduced data in order to verify the data. This results in another "modified unknown" quantity.

$$\text{reduced data} - \text{correction factors} = \text{original data (?) } \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 illustrates the issue with the standard automated test approach to data presentation. The graphs show a correction factor being used to convert the data, typically a voltage, to the parameter being measured (i.e. field strength, current). The reduced data is then compared to the specification to determine compliance. The analyzer output is now unavailable to a reviewer.

When a reviewer receives large amounts of data, as with a multi-unit military system, the possibility of finding errors in the data reduction is greatly increased. The problem can be compounded further when engineering analysis is required in order to determine compliance with the applicable specification.

Overlooking Engineering Analysis : When obtaining broadband data the analyzer output must be examined, prior to any manipulation, in order to determine if the signals observed are broadband or narrowband. Also, depending on the type of broadband signal that is observed (correlated vs. uncorrelated), the bandwidth correction factor may change.

The MIL-STD- 461 broadband limits are given in amplitude (i.e. amperes or volts/meter) per 1.0 MHz bandwidth. However, broadband measurements are typically performed employing a measurement bandwidth other than 1.0 MHz. A bandwidth correction factor (BWC) is then subtracted from the data to adjust it to an equivalent 1.0 MHz bandwidth. The BWC is calculated as follows:

Figure 1 - Typical Method for ATE EMI Data Presentation

$$BWC = k \log \left(\frac{BW}{1.0 \text{ MHz}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where: BWC = bandwidth correction factor

k = constant dependent on type of signal being measured

BW = measurement system bandwidth in MHz (i.e. IF bandwidth)

The constant k is dependent on the type of signal that is being evaluated, and is given in Table 1.

The penalty paid when using automated measurement systems for broadband measurements is that k is assumed to be 20. This provides for a most stringent and possibly inaccurate evaluation.

Since the BWC is subtracted directly from the analyzer data, along with adding the other correction factors, it modifies the analyzer data and presents a distorted image of the original data. This makes it more difficult to examine the noise.

Some systems attempt to discriminate between narrowband and broadband signals, but do an inconsistent job of it. For example, Figures 2 & 3 show the same test done twice by a particular system and a 10 MHz clock signal being classified once as broadband, then narrowband the second time. This is a problem because the system is ~10 dB closer to meeting the specification when the signal is classified as broadband.

If a narrowband signal is 10 dB over specification, a person could run the test until the software classifies it as broadband, and pass the test.

Solutions

Training

Test engineers should be given specific instruction in the use of automated test systems. The manuals that come with ATE equipment are usually references, not tutorials, so engineers are forced to find test anomalies the hard way. ATE manufacturers should issue tutorials with several specific situations and examples, not just one sample configuration for illustration, to help eliminate retesting.

Proficiency in a software language is a big help, if not a prerequisite, in the use of ATE. Any test engineer who uses automation should be able to write and debug simple programs in the ATE software language.

Engineering

Real time analyses of all ambients should be conducted prior to and after testing. Computer controlled ambient cuts often miss transients.

Methods, besides having the test engineer present, for accurately monitoring lengthy tests, such as MIL-STD-461 RE01, should be generated. Trained technicians can monitor an analyzer set on free run and be told to watch for transients and record them

Actual analyzer output should be made available to the reviewer. A few of the data plots could have analyzer output and levels in dBV plotted right on them. If a reviewer is able to correlate with what the computer is doing to the analyzer output on a couple of plots, the confidence factor in that data set is higher.

k	Noise Type	Example
k = 0	Correlated noise	measurement BW > signal BW
k = 10	Uncorrelated noise	i.e. Johnson Noise
k = 20	Correlated noise	measurement BW < signal BW

Table 1 - Possible Values for k

Figure 2 - Narrowband 10 MHz Signal Classified as Narrowband

Figure 3 - Narrowband 10 MHz Signal Classified as Broadband

Modify the Limit : The graphs in Figure 4 show an approach that retains original data and is easily employable by automated measurement systems. The correction factor is used to convert the specification to the units of the test equipment (voltage or power). This modified specification can now be compared to the test equipment output to determine compliance.

If the correction factors were to be added to the respective specifications, the test equipment output would be available and the test results could easily be verified. This method indicates compliance and in no way compromises the advantages of using ATE.

Smarter Software: If the test engineer knows some of the characteristics of an EUT, it does him no good using existing software. Smarter software could record the effects of an EUT on analyzer data and make better selections on limit choices. The engineer would be able to inform the software of characteristics of the EUT, and expected impact on any given test.

Conclusions

Automated testing has many benefits, but test engineers must proceed cautiously in their use of automation. There are many inherent risks in letting something besides yourself do your work. The learning curve in the use of ATE is not always as quick as expected, and people who know a lot about EMI testing often know little about the key link in the ATE chain, the software.

For example, if an EUT has several chips with 20 MHz clock frequencies, software that uses the MIL-STD 462 three dB criteria to identify broadband signals might classify it as broadband due to "smearing" of the signal [3]. Intelligent software might override that criteria and correctly classify it as narrowband if it was first told of the nature of the EUT.

Figure 4 - Recommended Method for ATE EMI Data Presentation

The EMC testing software which is available to date (known to the authors) all tend to add all the required correction factors to the original data. This significantly increases the risk of providing the reviewer with bad data. It is therefore suggested that the correction factors be employed to modify the specification requirement and leave the original data untouched. This method retains all the benefits of the automated test equipment, reduces the risk of error and allows for verification of the test process.

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